

COMPREHENSIVE SUMMARY OF COURSES TAUGHT

This is in brief the courses (along with their major themes) taught while in university service

Undergraduate (UG) Courses

1. **Environmental Science and Disaster Management** – Course **Env. 111 (2+1)**, emphasizing **disaster management practices** and **environmental protection methods**.
2. **Elements of Agricultural Meteorology** – Courses **AGA-112 (1+1)** and **Agron-111 (1+1)**, addressing **meteorological principles** and **applications in agriculture**.
3. **Introductory Agrometeorology and Climate Change** – Course **Agron. 246 (1+1)**, focusing on **climate science** and its impacts on **crop productivity** and **sustainability**.
4. **Environmental Science and Disaster Management** – Course **Env. 311 (2+0)**, focusing on **environmental sustainability**, **ecological principles**, and **disaster preparedness strategies**.
5. **Weather Forecasting** – Course **Phys. 313 (3+0)**, introducing **fundamentals of weather prediction**, **forecasting techniques**, and their role in **agriculture**.
6. **Geoinformatics, Nano-Technology, and Precision Farming** – Course **Agron. 358 (1+1)**, covering **precision farming tools**, **remote sensing**, and **advanced agricultural technologies**.
7. **Agri-Informatics** – Course **Ag. Info. 361 (1+1)**, introducing **data-driven technologies** for **agriculture management** and **precision techniques**.
8. In addition to the listed courses, **special lectures on Organic Agriculture, Weed Management, and Animal Husbandry** were also conducted. These lectures provided **supplementary knowledge** and **practical insights** to address **modern agricultural challenges** effectively.

Postgraduate (PG) Courses

1. **Agroclimatology** – Course **AGA-402 (2+1)**, addressing **climatic variability**, **weather impacts**, and **climate-resilient farming**.
2. **Dry Land Agriculture** – Course **AGA-406 (2+1)**, focusing on **drought management**, **water conservation**, and **rainfed farming practices**.
3. **Agrometeorology and Crop Weather Forecasting** – Course **Agron. 505 (2+1)**, focusing on **advanced weather prediction**, **forecast models**, and their application to **crop-weather analysis**.
4. **E-Course on Disaster Management-PGS 505 (1+0) NC**, focusing on comprehensive knowledge on **disasters and their management**.

5. **Agricultural Meteorology** – Course **Agron. 561 (2+1)**, emphasizing various weather systems as related to agriculture and crop weather environment.
6. **Weather Forecasting** – Course **Agron. 562 (2+1)**, covering **forecasting systems, prediction tools, and field applications** in agriculture.

Key Observations

- The curriculum spans **fundamental courses** for **UG students** and **specialized research-focused programs** for **PG students**.
- Emphasis on **modern technologies** such as **Geoinformatics, Nano-Technology, and Agrometeorology** reflects advancements in **precision agriculture**.
- **Practical learning components**, including **weather forecasting, disaster management, and climate resilience**, preparing students for **real-world applications** and **research-driven solutions** in agriculture.